

Biofabrication of Atherosclerotic Plaques to Develop Ex-Vivo Stenotic Artery Model

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INTRODUCTION

Peripheral artery disease (PAD) is the narrowing or occlusion of arteries due to formation of plaques composed of cholesterol, calcium, collagen, and smooth muscle cells within the arterial wall¹. Preclinical testing of the drug delivery devices or therapeutics designed to treat PAD are often performed in ex-vivo models involving the use of healthy animal arteries without accounting for the in vivo presence, composition, and mechanical properties of the atherosclerotic plaque². Nevertheless, mimicking the plaque compositions and mechanical properties is very important to allow better understanding and to aid in better designing and evaluating drug delivery vehicles. This work is focused on mimicking American heart association classification (AHA) type VII and VIII plaques that are predominantly observed in superficial femoral artery (SFA), and that are majorly composed of calcium deposits and fibrotic tissue/collagen respectively³. We aim to reproduce human type VII and type VIII plaques in porcine arteries by designing injectable hydrogels, using gelatin and gelatin-based composite materials. Injectable plaques with different mechanical properties can be obtained by tuning the polymer, crosslinker and calcium salt concentrations to create stenosis in ex-vivo porcine artery. Gelatin, a hydrolyzed form of collagen, is chosen due to its chemical similarity to the sclerotic tissue of the plaque.

	Calcification	Fibrous tissue/collagen	Media	Lumen
Mimicking materials for ex vivo model	Calcium phosphate/Calcium carbonate salts	Gelatin and Gelatin/alginate	porcine artery	

Figure 1: Rationale for materials choice to biofabricate human SFA type VII and VIII mimicking plaques.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

0.5% – 10% w/v Gelatin and Gelatin-alginate solutions are prepared. Gelatin is dissolved in distilled water under continuous stirring at 60°C for 15 minutes, followed by addition of alginate (only for gelatin-alginate gels) at 37°C. To prepare type VII plaques, different concentrations of calcium carbonate and calcium phosphate salt forms are added to the solutions. Internal crosslinking is performed for gelatin and gelatin-alginate solutions with glutaraldehyde (GA) and glucono- δ -lactone (GDL) respectively. Type VIII plaque is mimicked using Gelatin gels without calcium salts. Gelling time and injectability of the various hydrogel

solutions are being assessed. The swelling properties and stability of the hydrogels in saline/PBS at 37°C are being studied by checking the weights at different time points for up to 72 hours. A mechanical analysis of the hydrogels and porcine arteries with injected hydrogel is currently ongoing. Preliminary tests were performed to assess that feasibility of injecting the developed hydrogels in porcine arteries (provided by a local abattoir). Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining of the artery with injected hydrogel is being performed.

Figure 2: Preparation of injectable hydrogels to create type VII plaques in porcine arteries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The performed preliminary tests demonstrated that the injection of hydrogel solutions into the porcine arterial wall is feasible, and that a plaque within the wall can be created (Figure 2). The location of the plaque within the artery wall is being confirmed by H&E. However, methods to control the shape and size of the obtained plaque are necessary and will be developed in the future. Gelatin-based injectable hydrogels are expected to be obtained with different mechanical stiffness.

CONCLUSION

Artificial plaques are created with compositions mimicking human atherosclerotic plaques in SFA using simple materials. This groundwork can be exploited to mimic various other AHA types of plaques such as fatty plaques by introducing cholesterol or other lipids into the hydrogels. This ex-vivo atherosclerotic model will be further developed to achieve different types of calcifications that can be used to assess the performance of drug coated balloons (DCB).

REFERENCES

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